

PARENTS' ADHERENCE TO CHILD IMMUNIZATION OF THE BADJAO COMMUNITY IN BARANGAY TAMBACAN, ILIGAN CITY

Honey Lou T. Caneos, Lovely Dawn P. Clemeña, Atasha Ella E. Lopez,
Julla P. Palanas, Ian C. Abordo, PhD, Shella G. Dello, RN, MAN, DM,
Ma Almira P. Nebres, RN, MAN, PhD

Nursing Department, Adventist Medical Center College, Iligan City, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13768517>

ABSTRACT

Despite increased efforts to expand immunization coverage, progress in reducing zero-dose children remains inadequate, particularly in urban and rural areas such as the Badjao community in Brgy. Tambacan, Iligan City. This qualitative case study aimed to explore adherence to child immunization among Badjao mothers by interviewing 15 parents of children aged 0-5. The findings reveal that adherence is significantly influenced by cultural beliefs, education, and support from healthcare professionals and family. While barriers such as viewing vaccines as treatments for illness, lack of education, and financial constraints persist, most literate and informed parents adhere to immunization schedules. The study highlights a cultural shift from traditional health practices toward the acceptance of modern medical interventions, indicating a growing recognition of the benefits of immunization within the community.

Keywords: *Badjao, child immunization, panday, tuhan, zero-dose children*

INTRODUCTION

Immunization is one of the most cost-effective public health initiatives, with an estimated 4.4 million deaths avoided each year among children (UNICEF 2023). It is considered more economical and effective than treating them. The eradication,

elimination, and significant depletion of vaccine-preventable diseases, extending life expectancy, demonstrate the effectiveness of vaccination.

The Immunization Agenda of WHO in 2021 to 2030 declared a global vaccination objective of these routine immunizations to 90% (UNICEF 2023). These vaccines have broadened the scope of vaccination protection to control infectious diseases and improve the health of all populations worldwide (WHO 2023). Thus, it is notable that these goals made a significant development since EPI was enacted globally (Malecosio et al. 2020).

However, regardless of this development, basic vaccination coverage has remained between 70 and 80% over the previous 30 years. EPI has never met its goal of fully immunizing at least 95% of children (Ulep and Uy, 2022). Reports revealed that around 14.3 million infants did not receive an initial dose of DTP vaccination, and another 6.2 million received partial vaccination (WHO, 2023). Globally, over three years, 67 million children missed vaccinations (UNICEF, 2023). In the Philippines, one million Filipino children lack a single dose of vaccine, placing them among the most unprotected against tuberculosis, measles, and pertussis (UNICEF, 2022).

In the Philippines, certain tribes incorporate rituals into their health practices. The Badjaos, one of these tribes, often labeled as uneducated, face societal discrimination, and making it difficult for them to adapt in modern society (Coady, 2019). Badjaos healthcare access is limited due to their reliance on their *Pandays*, compensated by their health practices. (Jondonero et al., 2016). In a study by Ty (2010), marginalized groups, face difficulties in accessing government facilities, especially health services. With that, health control practices in the indigenous group in the community are a rising problem that possibly yield catastrophic problems in the future (Lozano, 2001).

Therefore, despite increased efforts to expand immunization coverage, there has been low progress in reducing the number of zero-dose children. It continues to be a huge challenge to reach every child. Children with no, lacking, or incomplete vaccination are those situated in densely populated urban areas and remote rural areas (UNICEF, 2023). Parental barriers are fundamentals that delay the development of vaccination services and parental perceptions significantly impact children's immunization (Bangura et al., 2020).

Hence, our study will address knowledge gaps in such vulnerable groups, particularly in the Badjao community. The researchers chose the Badjao community because there is little literature that supports the awareness of Badjaos towards immunization. This will be used to address the adherence of parents to child immunization in marginalized areas. This study can be utilized to educate public health policies about barrier-reduction efforts. Moreover, will address the parent's adherence to childhood immunization.

Research Questions

The main research questions were:

1. What are the cultural beliefs of the Badjao community that are relevant to immunization?
 2. What are the barriers and challenges to adherence of Badjao parents to childhood immunization?
 3. What are the reasons of the Badjao parents for adhering to childhood immunization?
-

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative approach, particularly a collective case study to fully grasp the scenario and its significance in a social unit (Merriam 1998; Yin 2009). Through contrasting and comparing, the researchers are able to comprehend the phenomena being studied both within and between cases. This study is effective for a case study framework because it is contextual and focuses on a process (Merriam 1998).

The term bounded system refers to a research case defined by time, location, or specific physical boundaries, recognizing and understanding the limits of an organization for research (Creswell 2002). It involves establishing clear boundaries around the study object, which can include an individual, group, or community (Merriam 1998).

The researchers conducted in-depth interviews with 15 parents in the Badjao community to understand issues related to child immunization adherence. The following inclusion criteria of this study are: (1) a member of the Badjao community, (2) a parent with one or more children, (3) can speak and understand Bisaya language, and (4) willing to participate in the study.

Data Gathering Protocol

This study applied an open-ended interview. The researchers chose to interview as their data gathering protocol because according to (Burns and Grove 2013), interviews are a flexible method that enables the researcher to examine a greater depth of meaning than is possible with other methods, cooperation can be facilitated and more information can be elicited through the use of interpersonal skills, and responses to interviews are generally higher than those to questionnaires. An interview guide using open-ended questions was prepared to gather data. The interview was done in the local dialect, Cebuano or Visayan, to make the interview process easier for respondents who prefer the local language for the interviews. Before starting the interview, the researchers explained the reason and importance of this study.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers followed specific guidelines for conducting interviews, starting with seeking permission from the college dean through a formal letter, approved by their thesis adviser, ensuring voluntary participation and full disclosure of study objectives to selected respondents. Prior to interviews, participants were presented with all research details to obtain informed consent, ensuring security, privacy, and confidentiality

throughout the process. Interviews were conducted in suitable settings, with participants briefed on objectives, confidentiality, and interview details, utilizing conversational questions for flexibility. Privacy and confidentiality were prioritized, maintaining participants' anonymity and addressing concerns such as confidentiality, consent, and identity protection. Despite challenges, only information disclosed by participants was accessible to researchers, with meticulous documentation of interview data.

Data Gathering Procedures

The aim of this study was to comprehensively investigate a person, activity, or process of study, requiring intensive data collection (Merriam 1998; Yin 2003) and applying “various forms of data” (Creswell 2002). Data collection for case studies primarily highlighted one of the three references of data: observation, interviews, and information. The fundamentals of observation during data gathering included: area, participants, reaction, and conversation (Merriam 1998). Data was collected through formal interviewing to address our research question, followed by documentation of the data.

The study was carried out in Barangay Tambacan. The researchers wrote a letter to the barangay health center midwife and the barangay captain of Brgy. Tambacan, and received approval to conduct the study within their community. This study was conducted over three weeks.

Data were collected using open-ended questions. To ensure accuracy, the entire duration of the interview was recorded, and important details were written down for encoding purposes. Each question was asked separately to give the interviewee plenty of time to consider and respond. The researchers gave instructions to the 15 mothers and allotted 30 minutes to each respondent during the interview. Six (6) relevant questions were asked of the respondents. They were then given the freedom to answer and respond to the questions to prevent giving inaccurate information.

Data Analysis

After conducting the study, the data was analyzed thematically. The researchers applied the thematic analysis framework to examine the qualitative data. The researchers precisely investigated the data to identify similar themes that were often presented, such as topics, ideas, and patterns of definition (Caulfield 2019).

In the first phase, the researchers familiarized themselves with the data by transcribing the audio, reading the notes, and thoroughly skimming the information before starting to analyze and separate the items. In the second phase, the researchers coded the data by highlighting or creating abbreviations for sections, commonly lines or phrases.

After coding the phrases, the researchers began formulating themes in the third phase. This was helpful in determining relevant or irrelevant information. In the fourth phase, the researchers reviewed themes, taking accurate and useful descriptions of the themes. In the fifth phase, they defined and named the themes to decipher and

understand the information. Finally, in the sixth phase, they wrote up the entire analysis based on the extracted and formulated facts and themes.

Authenticity and Trustworthiness

To ensure the credibility of the data gathered, the researchers incorporated investigator triangulation to seek different interpretations of the data gathered from various perspectives of the researchers. An audit trail was also employed to assess raw data, formulate themes, and draw conclusions, maintaining a progress record of data collection and articulating the researchers' descriptions and observations during the interviews. Additionally, after gathering and transcribing the data, the researchers carried out member checking, to validate whether the researchers properly interpreted the participants' ideas. The process was conducted in an encouraging manner to promote truthfulness and reflection among the participants, thereby enhancing the quality of the data.

Reflexivity Statement

In the context of the study, the researchers, as nursing students, acknowledge that their pre-existing assumptions, experiences, and knowledge, particularly their understanding of the importance of childhood immunizations, may have influenced their approach. Intrigued by the adherence of the unique and marginalized Badjao community to this crucial aspect of healthcare, they have chosen to explore the intricacies of immunization adherence of this population. Aware of their potential bias and their possible influence on the study, the researchers mitigated these through rigorous data collection and analysis of methods, incorporated peer discussions or debriefing after each interview session to challenge their interpretations. They also engaged with the Badjao community in a respectful and culturally sensitive manner, prioritizing their perspectives rather than imposing their own views.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows the profile of the participants. All 15 participants were Badjao mothers who could speak and understand the Bisaya language. None of them were aware of their birthdays. One had 6 children, two had 5 children, three had 4 children, two had 3 children, one had one child, and four did not specify the number of children they had.

Table 1
Description of the Participants

Participants	Age	Number of Children
P1	Not aware of the birthday	Did not specify
P2	Not aware of the birthday	5
P3	Not aware of the birthday	Did not specify

P4	Not aware of the birthday	Did not specify
P5	Not aware of the birthday	3
P6	Not aware of the birthday	4
P7	Not aware of the birthday	Did not specify
P8	Not aware of the birthday	1
P9	Not aware of the birthday	2
P10	Not aware of the birthday	3
P11	Not aware of the birthday	5
P12	Not aware of the birthday	1

Cultural Beliefs of the Badjao Community on Immunization

When asked about the participants' cultural beliefs relevant to immunization, the participants' responses can be grouped into three (3) themes. The themes are (1) knowledge and attitudes towards vaccines, (2) cultural transition and adaptation; and (3) role of health centers in Badjao community

Theme 1: Knowledge and Attitudes Towards Vaccines.

Mothers perceived vaccines as a form of medicine that not only prevents illnesses but also promotes well-being. They regard it as medicine and is beneficial for their child. Thus, this knowledge fuels their positive attitude towards immunization and vaccines. They commented:

Participant 2: *"It's for preventing illness, for their well-being, that's why they should be vaccinated."*

Participant 3: *"Medicine. It's medicine for my child. It's beneficial."*

Theme 2: Cultural Transition and Adaptation.

The evolution of cultural norms and practices in the Badjao community in terms of health and wellness focuses on the transition from traditional health practices, which may not have included vaccination or immunization, towards the acceptance and incorporation of modern medical interventions like vaccines. This is highlighted in the following participants' responses:

Participant 6: *"Usually, we fear death. And secondly, we were not accustomed to getting vaccinated."*

Theme 3: Role of Health Centers in Badjao Community.

The significance of health centers within the Badjao community is highlighted by Participant 14's response, which underscores the assistance and education imparted by the Center to the community that facilitated acceptance and utilization of formal healthcare services, including immunization. They stated:

Participant 14: *"Vaccination is okay, it doesn't harm them. In the past, our ancestors didn't believe in immunization or prenatal care, that was their belief long ago. If they got sick, they didn't go to the doctor or city, they were afraid. Their belief was in Umbo and Tuhan. They used coconut husks, charcoal, and fire for their rituals. But now they have learned. I tell them to get a check-up for free because some children died due to their old beliefs. They used to give soft drinks like Royal and feed them, but now they know better. They also used to not deworm, but now they do. If they need medicine, I tell them to go to the center for check-ups for children aged 0-5, but for older ones, I can get the medicine."*

Reasons for Adhering to Childhood Immunization

When asked about the participants' reasons for adhering to childhood immunization, the participants' responses can be grouped into six (6) themes. The themes are (1) influence and trust in healthcare providers; (2) family and elders' influence; (3) motivation for protection and health, (4) adherence to recommendations; (5) risk assessment and observation; and (6) decision-making based on experience

Theme 1: Influence and Trust in Healthcare Providers.

Healthcare influence strongly encouraged mothers to trust medical professionals. Parents mentioned that they followed doctors' advice and recommendations. Thus, the authority of healthcare providers played a significant role in their decision-making process. They said:

Participant 1: *"The Doctor said so... For the child's good health..."*

Theme 2: Family and Elders' Influence.

Elders' wisdom and family opinions highly influenced mothers' decisions and perceptions regarding vaccination uptake. Participants considered piece of advice from their grandparents and older family members. They commented:

Participant 1: *"My grandfather said to get vaccinated..."*

Theme 3: Motivation for Protection and Health.

Mothers expressed concern for their children's well-being. They perceived vaccination as a protective measure to prevent illness and maintain optimal health for their children. They stated:

Participant 2: *“It’s for preventing illness, for their well-being”*

Theme 4: Adherence to Recommendations.

Many mothers strongly complied with and followed instructions from healthcare facilities or nurses. This showed that adherence to vaccination schedules and maintaining health records was essential. They mentioned:

Participant 4: *“They said at the hospital to take my child to the center. So, I took her there.”*

Theme 5: Risk Assessment and Observation.

Before adhering to vaccination uptake, some mothers observed others who were vaccinated and remained healthy. This observation demonstrates a careful assessment of risks before fully trusting the immunization process. They remarked:

Participant 14: *“We think about it, but we look at others who got vaccinated and nothing bad happened to them, so we join in because it doesn’t harm.”*

Theme 6: Decision-Making Based on Experience.

Personal experiences played a significant role in mothers’ choices. These experiences revealed that immunization is associated with better health outcomes for their children. They stated:

Participant 15: *“Because when my child was not vaccinated, and they got sick, the illness continued.”*

Challenges to Childhood Immunization Adherence

When asked about the participants’ beliefs on immunization, the participants’ responses can be grouped into six (6) themes. The themes are (1) education and awareness, (2) compliance for well-being, (3) trust and skepticism, (4) relocation and fear of death, (5) language and communication, and (6) financial constraints.

Theme 1: Education and Awareness.

Literacy challenges faced by the Badjao community further exacerbated their awareness barriers to adhering to childhood immunization. Mothers reported difficulties due to lack of information, education, and illiteracy, which made it hard for them to grasp the importance of immunization. They commented:

Participant 1: *“I didn’t return because they didn’t inform me... We’re Badjaos and we can’t read.”*

Theme 2: Compliance for Well-Being.

Participants demonstrated an understanding of following the immunization schedule and ensuring their child's well-being. Some mothers prioritized their children's health and followed immunization guidelines diligently. They said:

Participant 2: *"Yes, we comply. If we don't comply, the child won't get better."*

Theme 3: Trust and Skepticism.

The skepticism among Badjao mothers about vaccine safety and efficacy is a notable challenge. Their expressed doubts, fueled by fears of harmful or expired medicines, highlight the uncertainties and suspicions surrounding immunization. These concerns often stem from misinformation, limited understanding, or negative experiences. They mentioned:

Participant 13: *"We might be fooled. A friend told me not to just give anything to the children."*

Theme 4: Relocation and Fear of Death.

Frequent relocation caused barriers to immunization access and instilled fear among parents. The Badjao parents revealed that, due to frequent relocation and fear of death, they became reluctant to immunize their children. They said:

Participant 6: *"For Badjao children, they're kept hidden because they're scared of dying."*

Theme 5: Language and Communication.

Language differences between Bisaya and their native language created challenges and barriers to understanding explanations and reading information from healthcare providers. They remarked:

Participant 14: *"We understand if we ask, but reading, we don't understand."*

Theme 6: Financial Constraints.

It was discovered that money was one of the significant factors, with some mothers mentioning the need for funds to access healthcare services. They commented:

Participant 15: *"Yes, you need money; they won't entertain you if you don't have money."*

Summary of Themes

These show the summary of themes. The first research question has three (3) themes: (1) knowledge and attitudes towards vaccines; (2) cultural transition and

adaptation; and (3) role of health centers in the Badjao community. The second research question has six (6) themes: (1) influence and trust in healthcare providers; (2) family and elders' influence; (3) motivation for protection and health; (4) adherence to recommendations; (5) risk assessment and observation; and (6) decision-making based on experience. The third research question has six (6) themes: (1) education and awareness; (2) compliance for well-being; (3) trust and skepticism; (4) relocation and fear of death; (5) language and communication; and (6) financial constraints. Each theme is given a brief description of what it entails.

Table 2
Summary of Themes

Cultural Beliefs of the Badjao Community on Immunization

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Descriptions</i>
Knowledge and Attitudes Towards Vaccines	Understanding of vaccines within the Badjao community's cultural context. This explores their perception of vaccines as a form of medicine that not only prevents illnesses but also promotes well-being. The indication of a broad understanding and acceptance of vaccines within their community is supported by the participants' insights.
Cultural Transition and Adaptation	The evolution of cultural norms and practices in the Badjao community in terms of health and wellness focuses on the transition from traditional health practices, which may not have included vaccination or immunization, towards the acceptance and incorporation of modern medical interventions like vaccines.
Role of Health Centers in Badjao Community	The significance of health centers within the Badjao community is highlighted by Participant 14's response, which underscore the assistance and education imparted by the Center to the community that facilitated acceptance and utilization of formal healthcare services, including immunization.

Reasons for Adhering to Childhood Immunization

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Description</i>
Influence and Trust in Healthcare Providers	Healthcare influence can strongly encourage mothers to trust medical professionals. Parents mentioned that they follow doctors' advice and recommendations. Thus, the authority of healthcare providers plays a significant role in their decision-making process.
Family and Elders' Influence	Elders' wisdom and family opinions highly influence mothers' decisions and perceptions regarding vaccination uptake.

	Participants considered advice from their grandparents and older family members.
Motivation for Protection and Health	Mothers expressed concern for their children's well-being. They perceive vaccination as a protective measure to prevent illness and maintain optimal health for their children.
Adherence to Recommendation	Many mothers strongly complied with and followed instructions from healthcare facilities or nurses. This showed that adherence to vaccination schedules and maintaining health records were essential.
Risk Assessment and Observation	Before adhering to vaccination uptake, some mothers observed others who were vaccinated and remained healthy. This observation demonstrates a careful assessment of risks before fully trusting the immunization process.
Decision-Making Based on Experience	Personal experiences played a significant role in mothers' choices. These experiences revealed that immunization is associated with better health outcomes for their children.

Challenges to Childhood Immunization Adherence

<i>Themes</i>	<i>Description</i>
Education and Awareness	Literacy challenges faced by the Badjao community further exacerbated their awareness barriers to adhering to childhood immunization. Mothers reported difficulties due to lack of information, education, and illiteracy, which made it hard for them to grasp the importance of immunization.
Compliance for Well-Being	Participants demonstrated an understanding of following the immunization schedule and ensuring their child's well-being. Some mothers prioritized their children's health and followed immunization guidelines diligently.
Trust and Skepticism	The skepticism of Badjao mothers regarding the safety and efficacy of vaccines poses a challenge. Mothers expressed doubts about vaccination, fearing harmful or expired medicines. This illustrates the doubts, uncertainties, and suspicions harbored by Badjao mothers about immunization, often fueled by misinformation, lack of understanding, or negative experiences.
Relocation and Fear of Death	Frequent relocation caused barriers to immunization access and instilled fear among parents. The Badjao parents revealed that, due to frequent relocation and fear of death, they became reluctant to immunize their children.

Language and Communication

Language differences between Bisaya and their native language created challenges and barriers to understanding explanations and reading information from healthcare providers.

Financial Constraints

It was discovered that money was one of the significant factors, with some mothers mentioning the need for funds to access healthcare services.

Concept Map of Themes

This shows the concept map of parent’s adherence to child immunization in the Badjao community in Brgy. Tambacan, Iligan City. The research questions are written below the research title along with their respective themes. One (1) research question has three (3) themes, while the other two have six (6) themes.

Figure 1: Concept Map

DISCUSSION

The results of the study indicated that adherence to childhood immunization among Badjao mothers varied due to several factors. Cultural beliefs significantly influence adherence, primarily because of their understanding and perception of vaccines. While parents generally knew that vaccines prevent diseases, some viewed

them as treatments administered only when children were ill. Traditional health norms in the community have gradually adapted to modern practices such as immunization and professional healthcare. The study found that the primary reasons for adherence were the influence, trust, and recommendations of healthcare professionals, families, and the elderly. Key obstacles include a lack of education and awareness, language and communication issues, and skepticism, which lead to uncertainty and suspicion about immunization. Overall, the researchers found that most of the Badjao parents interviewed adhered to childhood immunization. Additionally, parents who were literate, informed, and trusting of the immunization process were more likely to ensure that their children received vaccines.

The findings align with previous studies highlighting a lack of information and encouragement among parents is a critical issue for improving immunization rates (Tiwari et al., 2019). The Badjao community's literacy challenges exacerbate barriers to childhood immunization, with mothers reporting difficulties due to lack of information, education, and illiteracy (Steens et al., 2020). The study revealed that adherence to childhood immunization among Badjao mothers is influenced by their understanding of vaccines and the role of health centers. Low immunization coverage is often attributed to myths, misconceptions, and fears about vaccines (Muhammad et al., 2023). Findings from Ellis et al. (2020) show that mothers often adopt the immunization views and beliefs of their mothers and grandparents, highlighting the strong influence of family opinions on vaccination decisions.

The study also emphasizes that trust in healthcare professionals, family influence, and the desire to protect children are key drivers of Badjao mothers' commitment to immunization. This aligns with Schellenberg et al. (2023), who highlighted the role of trust in shaping parental perspectives on vaccinations. Our findings indicate that Badjao mothers' personal experiences play a significant role in their decision to immunize their children, reinforcing the belief that immunization leads to better health outcomes. In contrast, previous literature (Ellithorpe et al., 2022) noted that mothers with unvaccinated children rely on family for vaccination information, adopting beliefs passed down by their elders.

Our findings indicate a cultural transition in the Badjao community. Previous literature has shown that the Badjaos, who uphold traditional health rituals, face difficulties accessing health services and primarily consult their pandays. Our study reveals an evolution in their health practices, with a shift from traditional methods to the acceptance of modern medical interventions, including child immunizations and vaccines.

The findings of this study are significant for public health strategies targeting the Badjao community. Firstly, the reliance of Badjao mothers on personal experiences for deciding to immunize their children highlights the importance of real-world testimonials and stories in promoting vaccination. Health programs should incorporate narratives and examples from within the community to foster greater acceptance and adherence to immunization.

Secondly, the trust placed by Badjao mothers in healthcare providers suggests that these professionals play a crucial role in influencing immunization decisions. Therefore, strengthening the relationship between healthcare providers and the Badjao community can enhance vaccination rates.

Furthermore, the observed cultural transition towards medical practices indicates a shift that health interventions can leverage. Recognizing this evolution allows for the development of culturally tailored health promotion strategies that respect traditional beliefs while promoting modern medical practices.

Additionally, addressing the difficulties in accessing health services for the Badjao community is essential. Creating outreach programs can mitigate these barriers, ensuring more children receive timely vaccinations. Involving pandays and respected community figures in vaccination campaigns can enhance the credibility and reach of these initiatives.

Overall, this study underscores the need for culturally informed, experience-based, and trust-centered approaches in promoting child immunization within the Badjao community.

Conclusions

In conclusion, adherence to vaccination among Badjao mothers varies due to several factors, with cultural beliefs significantly influencing their perceptions of vaccines. While some Badjao mothers view vaccines as preventive, others see them as treatments for illness and only comply when their child is sick. Low immunization rates are impacted by gaps in comprehension, limited access to healthcare facilities, resettlement issues, and doubt. Vaccination hesitancy is driven by illiteracy, financial constraints, and varying degrees of trust in healthcare providers.

However, our study highlights the significant role of personal experiences and cultural adaptation among Badjao mothers in shaping health and wellbeing practices. It reveals that traditional standards within the Badjao community are evolving, with a noticeable shift from exclusive reliance on traditional health practices to the acceptance and incorporation of modern medical interventions, such as child immunization. This evolution indicates a growing recognition of the benefits of immunization and a willingness to integrate contemporary healthcare methods into their cultural frameworks.

Recommendations

The researchers of this study recommend that future studies adopt a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative data collection with qualitative methods to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the community's experiences and perspectives on immunization. This approach will enable researchers to capture numerical data alongside in-depth personal insights, thereby enhancing the validity and reliability of the findings. Additionally, extending the study timeline is recommended to

better understand the long-term effects of immunization decisions, allowing for a clearer view of sustained adherence and its outcomes.

Future research should also include a broader range of Badjao communities to obtain more comprehensive and generalize insights, identifying commonalities and differences across various subgroups. Implementing these recommendations will provide a richer, more nuanced understanding of immunization practices within the Badjao community.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Regarding the conditions of this study, several ethical considerations were carefully addressed. The researchers adhered to a series of guidelines to ensure ethical and effective data collection. Permission was initially secured from the college dean through a formal letter, endorsed by their thesis adviser, to conduct in-person interviews. Participation was voluntary, and participants were informed about the study's objectives and their roles. Informed consent was obtained from participants, ensuring they understood the study details and agreed to participate voluntarily, with assurances of privacy and confidentiality. Permission was also obtained for audio recording the interviews.

No conflicts of interest were present, and the study was conducted with avoidance of plagiarism. The interviews were held in an appropriate setting where the objectives, format, and expectations were clearly explained. To allow for flexibility, the interviews were informal and conversational. Privacy and confidentiality were prioritized, with measures in place to protect participant's anonymity and secure their information. The researchers addressed potential biases by employing reflexivity, acknowledging how their own backgrounds and experiences might impact the study. They ensured that the interpretation of findings remained impartial and that the results were used exclusively for research purposes.

Acknowledgments

The fulfillment of this research paper, entitled Parents' Adherence to Child Immunization in the Badjao Community in Brgy. Tambacan, Iligan City, could not have been possible without the guidance and contributions of many people. The researchers would like to extend their heartfelt gratitude to these significant individuals:

Before everything, we praise the Lord for always hearing our prayers, especially for sustaining us with knowledge and wisdom, and for giving us strength and endurance throughout the study.

To our research director, Dr. Ian C. Abordo, PhD, thank you for your endless support and assistance until we accomplished our study. Thank you for sharing your expertise through mentoring us. Your meticulous feedback and ideas nurtured our research skills.

To our research adviser, Ms. Shella G. Dello, RN, MAN, DM, thank you for always monitoring and encouraging us to do our best in making this paper. Thank you for sharing your insights and ideas in honing this paper.

To our panelist, Mrs. Ma. Almira P. Nebres, RN, MAN, PhD, thank you for your constructive feedback during the presentation of this study, which broadened our perspective.

To the Barangay Kagawad of Barangay Tambacan, Mrs. Luzminda V. Fernandez, we thank you for dedicating your time and effort to welcoming and guiding us in your barangay.

Finally, to our respondents, we highly appreciate your time and effort in participating in our study. Without your notable answers, we would not have been able to complete this study.

REFERENCES

- Bangura JB, Xiao S, Qiu D, Ouyang F, Chen L. 2020. Barriers to childhood immunization in sub-Saharan Africa: A systematic review - BMC Public Health. BioMed Central. <https://bmcpublihealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12889-020-09169-4>
- Burns & Grove's understanding nursing research: building an evidence-based practice. 6th ed. Elsevier/Saunders.
- Caulfield J. 2019. How to Do Thematic Analysis. Scribbr. [accessed 2024 May 22]. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/thematic-analysis/>
- Coady H. 2019. Healthcare and beliefs in the Badjao tribe. SERVE. <https://serve.ie/healthcare-and-beliefs-in-the-badjao-tribe/>. [accessed 2024 May 30, 2024]
- Creswell JW. 2002. Educational Research: Planning, Conducting, and Evaluating Quantitative and Qualitative Research. Upper Saddle River (NJ): Merrill Prentice Hall. SAGE Publications
- Department of Health (DOH). n.d. Expanded Program on Immunization. [accessed 2024 January 18] <https://doh.gov.ph/uhc/health-programs/expanded-program-on-immunization/>
- Ellis N, Walker-Todd E, Heffernan C. 2020. Influences on childhood immunization decision-making in London's Gypsy and Traveller communities. *British Journal of Nursing*. 29(14):822–826. doi:<https://doi.org/10.12968/bjon.2020.29.14.822>.
- Ellithorpe ME, Adams R, Aladé F. 2022. Parents' Behaviors and Experiences Associated with Four Vaccination Behavior Groups for Childhood Vaccine Hesitancy. *Maternal and Child Health Journal*. 26(2):280–288. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10995-021-03336-8>.
- Jondonero C, Mamauag M, Tabil V, Lomondot SH, Daco N, Longcob W, Coyoca GS. 2016. Health behavior and practices of the Badjaos: an implication to health intervention. *Int J Nurs Sci*. 2016; 6(2): 172-178. <https://scholarly.msuiit.edu.ph/pages/articledetails.php?artno=287&s=>
- Lozano R. 2001. Ongoing problems and issues in fixing Indigenous health. *Australian and New Zealand Journal of Public Health*, 25(6), 494-496.
- Malecosio S, Celis JL, Delicana K, Deopido A, Kang Bacale, KM., Labasan, VK, Ladio, RM., Militante, KM., Paguntalan, J., Sabusap, VE. 2020. Vaccination coverage and factors associated with incomplete childhood vaccination among children aged 12-59 months in Miagao, Iloilo, Philippines. <http://dx.doi.org/10.18203/2394-6040.ijcmph20202971>
- Merriam SB. 1998. *Qualitative Research and Case Study Applications in Education*. San Francisco (CA): Jossey-Bass Publishers.

- Muhammad A, Cheema DA. 2023. "Barriers to Childhood Vaccination in Urban Slums of Pakistan." *Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal*, vol. 29, no. 5, pp. 371–379. <https://doi.org/10.26719/emhj.23.062>. Accessed 27 Sept. 2023.
- Schellenberg N, Dietrich LM, Petrucka P, AM C. 2023. Predictors and impact of trust on vaccine decisions in parents of 2-year-old children in Canada: findings from the 2017 Childhood National Immunization Coverage Survey (cNICS). *BMC Public Health*. 23(1). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-023-16705-5>.
- Singh S, Sahu D, Agrawal A, Vashi MD. 2019. "Barriers and Opportunities for Improving Childhood Immunization Coverage in Slums: A Qualitative Study." *Preventive Medicine Reports*, vol. 14, p. 100858. DOI:10.1016/j.pmedr.2019.100858. Accessed 12 June 2020.
- Steens A, Stefanoff P, Daae A, Vestrheim DF, Riise Bergsaker MA. 2020. High overall confidence in childhood vaccination in Norway, slightly lower among the unemployed and those with a lower level of education. *Vaccine*. 38(29):4536–4541. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2020.05.011>.
- Tiwari DA, Vishwakarma DK. 2019. A study of knowledge, attitude and practice of mothers on immunization of children in urban slums. *Pediatric Review: International Journal of Pediatric Research*. 6(10):547–554. doi:<https://doi.org/10.17511/ijpr.2019.i10.09>.
- Ty M. 2010. Challenges in public health facilities and services: evidence from a geographically isolated and disadvantaged area in the Philippines. *Journal of Global Health Reports*. 4:e2024. doi:<https://doi.org/10.29392/joghr.3.e2019059>
- UNICEF. 2023. The State of the World's Children 2023 | UNICEF. www.unicef.org; [accessed 2023 November 20] <https://www.unicef.org/reports/state-worlds-children-2023>.
- World Health Organization (WHO). 2023. Immunization coverage. *Who.int*. [accessed 2024 January 8] <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/immunization-coverage>
- Yin RK. 2003. *Case Study Research: Design and Methods*. 3rd ed. Thousand Oaks (CA): Sage Publications.
- Yin RK. 2009. *Case Study Research: Design and Methods*. 4th ed. Thousand Oaks (CA): Sage Publications.
-